

D4.2

Evaluation Report of the NGI Sargasso Programme 1

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Abstract

This report provides a comprehensive assessment of the NGI Sargasso Programme, detailing the evaluation and outcomes of activities aimed at supporting innovation in the NGI ecosystem. The report includes quantitative and qualitative analyses of the services provided by the OnCampus Programme, reflecting on their effectiveness based on feedback from participants. It covers various phases of the programme for the two cohorts of participants as of June 2024. The document also highlights lessons learned and suggests areas for improvement.

Keywords

NGI Sargasso, Evaluation, Lean Startup Methodology, Coaching, Mentoring, Business Model Canvas.

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<i>CL</i>	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC
<i>CO</i>	Confidential to NGI Sargasso project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

M	Month
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Executive summary

This evaluation report provides a detailed assessment of the NGI Sargasso Programme, which aims to support innovation within the Next Generation Internet (NGI) ecosystem. The report analyses the services offered through the OnCampus Programme using both quantitative and qualitative methods, focusing on the program's effectiveness and impact as of June 2024. The evaluation covers two cohorts of participants, offering insights into the programme's implementation, including coaching, mentoring, inspirational talks, and flipped classroom sessions. The report concludes with lessons learned and recommendations for future improvements.

Key findings include:

- ❑ **Regular feedback from participants and coaches has been instrumental in refining the program. Surveys indicate a high level of satisfaction with the support and resources provided.**
- ❑ **Participants highly rated the coaching sessions, with the first cohort giving an average score of 4.17 out of 5, and the second cohort 4.83 out of 5. Mentoring sessions were also well-received, with a 98.61% attendance rate in the first cohort and 100% in the second cohort.**
- ❑ **Inspirational talks and flipped classroom sessions were positively evaluated, highlighting their role in fostering creativity and strategic thinking. The average scores for inspirational talks were 7.44 (first cohort) and 7.78 (second cohort) out of 10.**
- ❑ **The Business Model Canvas, a core component of the program, received high evaluations from coaches, with the first cohort averaging 9.38 out of 10 and the second cohort 8.56 out of 10.**
- ❑ **The program has evolved through iterative feedback and retrospective workshops, ensuring that it meets the dynamic needs of the NGI ecosystem.**

The report emphasizes the program's success in providing support to innovation projects and suggests areas for improvement, including enhanced engagement strategies and refined service offerings.

Introduction

The NGI Sargasso Programme, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme, is designed to foster innovation within the NGI ecosystem by supporting early-stage projects through a comprehensive suite of services. These services include coaching sessions, mentoring sessions, inspirational talks, flipped classroom sessions, video lectures, and interviews with the ecosystem.

The following sections provide a detailed analysis of the services provided, their effectiveness, and the feedback received from participants. The report concludes with lessons learned and recommendations for future programme enhancements.

Task 4.4.

The NGI Sargasso programme employs the Lean Startup Methodology not only in its approach to third-party projects but also in the overarching methodology used to provide business and technical services. Consequently, the NGI Sargasso programme is designed with a flexible attitude, aiming to deliver optimal support to our "customers," the teams selected through the open calls. At the conclusion of each cohort, we conduct internal retrospective workshops to thoroughly analyze the service provision and its impact on the selected teams. These workshops encompass an evaluation of the feedback received from the teams about the mentoring, coaching, and training sessions. Through this process, partners have the opportunity to suggest replacements, modifications, or the addition of new services to better meet the evolving needs of the teams throughout the project's duration.

During the consortium meeting in Brussels in November 2023, together with the partners, we started to share lessons learned during the start of the first cohort, in order to improve the implementation of the second cohort. This task has been evolving during the weekly consortium meetings, improving the programme in a progressive way and with continuous implementation of improvements, and addressing any potential risks and issues.

During the MWCongress in Barcelona 2024, and with the possibility of meeting physically with coaches and beneficiaries, the consortium had the opportunity to hear insights about the OnCampus programme, its development as well as their satisfaction.

Lean Startup Methodology

The Lean Startup Method, adopted by the NGI Sargasso programme, comprises the following phases:

- BUILD: develop an initial plan, leveraging the significant expertise and resources of the partners, each a leader in their respective fields.**
- MEASURE: establish a monitoring and analysis framework, supported by a comprehensive toolkit for both quantitative and qualitative assessment, to collect evidence and feedback on the program's adoption.**
- LEARN: at the conclusion of each cohort, conduct a thorough analysis of the project to ensure alignment with the NGI ecosystem's needs and the participating teams' expectations.**

The insights from this phase are integrated into Work Packages 3 and 4, which are responsible for updating the open call and experimental program. This may include modifications to existing services or the introduction of new services as required. The findings from these analyses are utilized to prepare the Evaluation Report of the NGI Sargasso program.

Evaluation of the OnCampus Programme

Coaching Sessions

Coaching sessions, as outlined in the D4.1. Service Booklet deliverable, are structured one-on-one meetings with coaches designed to ensure team progress and alignment with the program's objectives and milestones. These sessions guide teams towards achieving their short and long-term business goals while addressing any misalignment or conflicts during project implementation. Each month, three 45-minute sessions are scheduled at times convenient for both the teams and the coaches, often consolidated into two sessions lasting one to one and a half hours.

The results of the coaching sessions were reported by both coaches and participating teams through feedback forms on the Sploro platform (there will be more details about the grantees feedback in the “feedback surveys” section).

The following Table 1 presents the number of coaching sessions attended by each team of the first cohort for each month of the OnCampus Programme as of May 31, 2024. The length of the session depends on the availability and workflow of the cohort beneficiaries, covering 2 hours and 15 min a month.

Team	Coach	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	Total
D3ICA	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	16
EBSI-CAN	Marc Sansó	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	16
INTEROP4DI D	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	16
SBAS	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	16

EVORAN	Juan Juan	2	16							
DDIP	Juan Juan	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	14
SNDS	Marc Sansó	2	16							
APSIDE	Marc Sansó	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	13

TABLE 1. NUMBER OF MONTHLY COACHING SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM OF THE 1ST COHORT.

Similarly, Table 2 provides the number of coaching sessions attended by each team of the second cohort for each month of the OnCampus Programme as of May 31, 2024. The length of the session depends on the availability and workflow of the cohort beneficiaries, covering 2 hours and 15 min a month.

Team	Coach	M1	M2	M3	Total
DES	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	1	2	2	5
DDP-CRC	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	6
HPQCSI	Juan Juan	2	2	2	6
Melisseus	Juan Juan	1	1	1	3
RSFA	Juan Juan	2	2	2	6
SIDIHub	Juan Juan	2	2	2	6
Trustless Democracy	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	1	2	2	5
VeriRecruit	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	6
GUARDIAN	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	2	2	2	6

TABLE 2. NUMBER OF MONTHLY COACHING SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM OF THE 2ND COHORT.

Table 3 provides an overview of the scores for the perceived effectiveness of the coaching sessions for the first cohort experiments, as evaluated by each participating team. These evaluations were conducted for the coaching sessions across the three stages of the programme. The scoring criteria used by the teams to assess the relevance and impact of the coaching sessions are as follows: 5 - very relevant, 4 - relevant, 3 - neutral, 2 - somewhat relevant, and 1 - not relevant.

Team	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Average Score
D3ICA	5	4	3	4.00

EBSI-CAN	5	5	5	5.00
INTEROP4DID	2	3	4	3.00
SBAS	5	4	5	4.67
EvORAN	5	4	4	4.33
DDIP	4	2	4	3.33
SNDS	5	5	5	5.00
APSIDE	4	4	4	4.00
Average Score	4.38	3.88	4.25	4.17

TABLE 3. SCORES OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE COACHING SESSIONS FROM THE 1ST COHORT.

On average, the teams of the first cohort rated their coaching sessions 4.17 out of 5.

FIGURE 1. AVERAGE EVALUATION OF THE COACHING SESSIONS BY THE TEAMS OF THE 1ST COHORT.

In a similar vein, the following table provides the scores for the perceived effectiveness of the coaching sessions for the second cohort experiments during the first and second stages of the programme, as evaluated by the participating teams.

Team	Stage 1	Stage 2	Average Score
DES	4	5	4.50
DDP-CRC	5	5	5.00
HPQCSI	5	5	5.00
Melisseus	5	5	5.00
RSFA	5	5	5.00
SIDIHub	5	5	5.00
Trustless Democracy	4	5	4.50
VeriRecruit	5	4	4.50

GUARDIAN	5	5	5.00
Average Score	4.78	4.89	4.83

TABLE 4. SCORES OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE COACHING SESSIONS FROM THE 2ND COHORT.

FIGURE 2. AVERAGE EVALUATION OF THE COACHING SESSIONS BY THE TEAMS OF THE 2ND COHORT.

The data presented both in Table 4 and in Figure 2 illustrate that teams of the second cohort have highly valued their coaching sessions within both the first and the second stages of the OnCampus programme, assigning an average score of 4.83 out of 5. This high level of satisfaction underscores the significant impact and value of these coaching sessions, which highlights their effectiveness in contributing to the participant teams' development and progress, as established by the goals of the NGI Sargasso.

The following tables provide some comments about the coaching sessions from the teams of the first and second cohort experiments.

Team	Comment
D3ICA	“... appreciated to get support from the coach for reminding us the key expectations of the program, together with being able to answer some questions we may have.”
EBSI-CAN	“Beyond a coach, he is a partner in our journey, adept at translating complex concepts into actionable steps.”
INTEROP4DID	“Beyond his technical expertise, Jordi brings a positive attitude to the table, creating a motivating and uplifting atmosphere within the team. His insights and guidance have been instrumental in our understanding of program requirements, and he plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of our deliverables.”
SBAS	“I really wish all teams had such a great coach. He is both very efficient and motivating. Also, he was always very accommodating. Moreover, he helps me through the items, including the business canvas, the hypotheses, the use cases creation, the interviews, the

	KPIs and the final report. He definitely offered a complementary view on the project and opened our eyes on many things.”
EvORAN	“We are working with the coach on positioning properly our product in the market. We are also discussing together with the coach about all the issues that we have found during the deployment.”
DDIP	“The coaching sessions with Juan have proved to be invaluable, not only in guiding our strategic direction but also in fostering innovative thinking regarding potential indirect revenue streams for our solutions.”
SNDS	“...he always provides guidance and feedback that is helpful and to the point. In the beginning I was apprehensive about having a meeting every couple of weeks, but as it turns out, there is zero wasted time during the meetings, and they serve as intermediate milestones...”
APSIDE	“Coaching sessions are important as they help us to iron out the details regarding the ways we present our technical work and vision, how the business model could be extended to cover additional customer segments and revenue streams.”

TABLE 5. SOME COMMENTS ON THE COACHING SESSIONS FROM THE 1ST COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Team	Comment
DES	“The regular check-ins and detailed feedback sessions have kept us accountable and focused, ensuring we make steady progress.”
DDP-CRC	“Our coach provided an exceptional experience, creating a very friendly atmosphere that made us feel comfortable and supported. We received super positive feedback throughout our sessions, which was incredibly motivating.”
HPQCSI	“Juan is very helpful and is especially beneficial for our project. His advice in the focus and progress of the project has been very useful.”
Melisseus	“Juan has been very helpful and dedicated. Despite the novelty of our topic, he kept on top of things and manage to help us focus on the important steps.”
RSFA	“Very efficient, smiling, business driven, mindful of our time.”
SIDIHub	“One of the coach’s most notable strengths lies in his ability to challenge us constructively. By probing our assumptions and

	encouraging us to reconsider our strategies, he has pushed us to think critically.”
Trustless Democracy	“The regular check-ins and detailed feedback sessions have kept us accountable and focused, ensuring we make steady progress. We are grateful for his commitment and look forward to continuing our work together.”
VeriRecruit	“He is giving constant support to the project and helping me to reach the objectives.”
GUARDIAN	“...he brings new ideas and approaches and helps us to identify possible weaknesses, without forgetting to highlight the things we do well. He tries to advise us with respect and when we have sent him an email with any specific question, he has always responded very quickly.”

TABLE 6. SOME COMMENTS ON THE COACHING SESSIONS FROM THE 2ND COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Mentoring Sessions

Mentoring sessions, as outlined in the D4.1. Service Booklet deliverable, in the OnCampus programme, provide teams with specialised expert knowledge through a series of online webinars that cover essential topics in business development, such as opportunity assessment, product validation, marketing strategy, business models, and fundraising, among others.

The monitoring of each team's participation in mentoring sessions was conducted during every session.

Table 7 provides a detailed overview of the number of mentoring sessions (webinars) attended by each team of the first cohort.

Team	Number of Mentoring Sessions Attended
D3ICA	9
EBSI-CAN	9
INTEROP4DID	9
SBAS	9
EVORAN	9

DDIP	9
SNDS	9
APSIDE	8

TABLE 7. NUMBER OF MENTORING SESSIONS ATTENDED BY TEAMS OF THE 1ST COHORT.FIGURE 3. AVERAGE ATTENDANCE OF THE MENTORING SESSIONS BY THE TEAMS OF THE 1ST COHORT.

As shown in Table 7, seven out of the eight teams from the first cohort attended all nine mentoring sessions offered by the OnCampus Programme. Only one team, APSIDE, attended eight sessions, missing one. The average attendance rate for the mentoring sessions among teams from the 1st cohort of the NGI Sargasso programme, as illustrated in Figure 3, was 98.61%. It is important to note that within the rules of the NGI Sargasso programme, any missed mentoring sessions cannot be made up in subsequent stages. This has a direct impact on the financial compensation teams receive at the end of each stage.

Similarly, the following table 8 provides an overview of the number of mentoring sessions attended by each team of the second cohort. It is important to highlight that for the second cohort experiments, 10 mentoring sessions were conducted, with 9 mandatory and 1 optional. Therefore, the maximum number reflected in the following table is 9, which corresponds to 100% of the KPI for the attendance of webinars concerning the subsequent stage payments.

Team	Number of Mentoring Sessions Attended
DES	9
DDP-CRC	9
HPQCSI	9

Melisseus	9
RSFA	9
SIDIHub	9
Trustless Democracy	9
VeriRecruit	9
GUARDIAN	9

TABLE 8. NUMBER OF MENTORING SESSIONS ATTENDED BY TEAMS OF THE 2ND COHORT.FIGURE 4. AVERAGE ATTENDANCE OF THE MENTORING SESSIONS BY THE TEAMS OF THE 2ND COHORT.

As shown in Table 8, all nine teams of the second cohort attended all nine compulsory mentoring sessions provided by the OnCampus Programme without any absences. Consequently, the average attendance rate for the mentoring sessions among the second cohort of the NGI Sargasso Programme, as depicted in Figure 4, was 100%.

The evaluations of the mentoring sessions were reported by each participating team through feedback forms on the Sploro platform.

The table below presents the detailed scores for each mentoring session conducted for the first cohort, where each team evaluated all nine webinars. The evaluations are based on a scale from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating "very relevant," 4 "relevant," 3 "neutral," 2 "somewhat relevant," and 1 "not relevant." This scoring system reflects the participants' perceived relevance and applicability of the content delivered during these webinars to their projects.

Title	D3ICA	EBSI-CAN	INTERO P4DID	SBAS	EvORAN	DDIP	SNDS	APSIDE	Average Score
How to connect with Corporations	3	5	2	4	3	5	5	5	4.00

How to protect the knowledge and results of innovation? Intellectual Property	4	5	3	4	4	4	5	5	4.25
Maximizing your Marketing impact: Tips and Tactics	4	5	2	4	4	2	4	4	3.63
How to tackle public funding?	4	5	2	4	4	1	4	4	3.50
Entrepreneurial finance	4	5	2	4	4	1	5	4	3.63
How to run your regulatory aspects? Legal Advisory	4	5	3	4	3	4	3	3	3.63
Standardization	3	5	3	4	5	1	4	3	3.50
How to pitch like an entrepreneur? Investment Pitch	4	5	4	4	4	1	5	4	3.88
What do investors expect? Fundraising	5	5	4	4	4	2	4	4	4.00
Average Score	3.89	5.00	2.78	4.00	3.89	2.33	4.33	4.00	3.78

TABLE 9. SCORES OF EACH MENTORING SESSION FROM THE 1ST COHORT.

Similarly, the table below presents the detailed scores for each mentoring session conducted for the second cohort experiments.

Title	DES	DDP-CRC	HPQCS I	Melisseus	RSFA	SIDI Hub	Trustless Democracy	VeriRecruit	GUARDIAN	Average Score
Setting the foundations of your start-up team	4	4	4	5	1	4	4	5	5	4.00
Standardisation and Open Source	4	3	4	4	2	5	4	4	3	3.67

How to protect the knowledge and results of innovation?	4	3	5	4	2	5	4	3	4	3.78
How to take the most from events - Tips for trade shows and networking	2	4	5	4	1	3	2	4	4	3.22
Online pitching made simple	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4.67
Maximizing Your Marketing Impact: Tips and Tactics	4	4	3	5	1	2	4	4	4	3.44
GDPR Made Simple	4	5	4	4	1	4	4	5	5	4.00
Impacts of AI on Communication	4	5	5	5	1	5	4	5	3	4.11
How to tackle public funding	5	4	5	3	5	4	5	4	4	4.33
Pitch Practice	5	4	4	5	3	3	5	5	4	4.22
Average Score	4.10	4.00	4.40	4.40	2.20	3.90	4.10	4.30	4.10	3.94

TABLE 10. SCORES OF EACH MENTORING SESSION FROM THE FIRST STAGE OF THE 2ND COHORT.

The findings indicate that the average rating for the mentoring sessions of the first cohort was 3.78 out of 5, while the second cohort rated their sessions slightly higher, with an average score of 3.94 out of 5. This suggests a generally positive perception of the mentoring sessions, with a slight improvement in participant satisfaction from the first to the second cohort. These ratings, along with qualitative feedback, are taken into account in planning mentoring sessions for the upcoming cohorts to improve their quality and relevance for future participants.

Inspirational Talk Sessions

The OnCampus programme offers two inspirational talks for each cohort, aimed at providing thought-provoking insights, sparking creativity, and inspiring participants to reach new heights in their projects (more details in the D4.1. Service Booklet deliverable). For the first cohort, the inspirational talks include "How Many Internets Should We Have" and "Linux Foundation as a Host For Transatlantic Cooperative Projects." The second cohort's talks are "Aligning Innovation with Social Justice" and "Software in the European Regulatory Landscape."

The monitoring of each team's participation in inspirational talks, similar to the mentoring sessions, was conducted during each of the two inspirational talk sessions.

As illustrated in Figure X, all the teams from both the first and second cohorts have fully attended both of the inspirational talk sessions, offered by the OnCampus Programme. This unanimous participation underscores the teams' collective commitment to the NGI Sargasso programme.

FIGURE 5. AVERAGE ATTENDANCE OF THE INSPIRATIONAL TALK SESSIONS BY THE TEAMS OF THE 1ST AND 2ND COHORTS

The forthcoming table delineates the scores for each inspirational talk session of the first cohort, where every participating team assessed the two inspirational talks presented. Evaluation scores range from 0 to 10, providing a spectrum for participants to rate the talks based on their inspirational value and relevance to their projects.

Team	Inspirational Talk 1 "How Many Internets Should We Have"	Inspirational Talk 2 "Linux Foundation as a Host For Transatlantic Cooperative Projects"	Average Score
D3ICA	8	7	7.50
EBSI-CAN	10	10	10.00
INTEROP4DID	1	5	3.00
SBAS	9	8	8.50
EvORAN	6	9	7.50
DDIP	7	7	7.00
SNDS	10	5	7.50

APSIDE	8	9	8.50
Average Score	7.38	7.50	7.44

TABLE 11. SCORES OF EACH INSPIRATIONAL TALK SESSION OF THE 1ST COHORT.

Similarly, the table below compiles the scores for each inspirational talk session of the second cohort, as evaluated by the participating teams.

Team	Inspirational Talk 1 "Aligning Innovation with Social Justice"	Inspirational Talk 2 "Software in the European Regulatory Landscape"	Average Score
DES	9	9	9.00
DDP-CRC	8	9	8.50
HPQCSI	9	9	9.00
Melisseus	10	9	9.50
RSFA	0	3	1.50
SIDIHub	8	7	7.50
Trustless Democracy	9	9	9.00
VeriRecruit	5	7	6.00
GUARDIAN	10	10	10.00
Average Score	7.56	8.00	7.78

TABLE 12. SCORES OF THE INSPIRATIONAL TALK SESSION OF THE FIRST STAGE OF THE 2ND COHORT.

The average score for the inspirational talk sessions, as evaluated by each team of the first cohort, is 7.44 out of 10. Similarly, the teams of the second cohort evaluated the inspirational talks, giving them an average score of 7.78 out of 10. These evaluations reflect a generally positive reception of the sessions and talks, indicating that they were effective and well-received by the participants.

The following tables provide some comments about the Inspirational Talk sessions from the teams of the first and second cohort experiments.

Team	Comment
D3ICA	"Interesting presentation"

EBSI-CAN	“The inspirational talk clearly resonates with the EBSI-CAN project towards building trust in new technologies.”
INTEROP4DID	“Not too much new information”
EvORAN	“It is an interesting analysis of the digital reality that we are buidling... that the way how it was presented was much more attractive than overall research presentations.”
DDIP	“While the session may prove beneficial for newcomers to such grant schemes, we find ourselves already acquainted with the processes and requirements associated with them.”
SNDS	“I ... found the viewpoint of the presenter very relevant to what we are doing (the vehicular Internet). The speaker was engaging, and thought provoking, plus he asked specific people to join in with their thoughts.”
APSIDE	“The inspirational talk was insightful and enabled us to rethink of approach and explore new ways of gathering/evaluating commercial-related information. It helped us to rethink the core assumptions of our technical and business work.”

TABLE 13. SOME COMMENTS ON THE INSPIRATIONAL TALK SESSIONS FROM THE 1ST COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Team	Comment
DES	“During the talk, we received great feedback from both the coach and the other participants, which was extremely valuable in refining our project approach. The interactive format facilitated meaningful exchanges and provided insights that we have actively incorporated into our work.”
DDP-CRC	“...the activity to put our project into a general context and create an awareness of our projects positioning was great.”
HPQCSI	“The inspirational talk was interesting. It made it all the more evident as to why our project is essential for supporting all individuals identities.” “The inspirational talk on the regulation environment in the European Union was ... interesting. The topic is very important especially when one begins to keep track of the changes in standards and requirements of digital identities as well as cryptography.”

Melisseus	“...is very important and helps everyone understand the importance of our proposal.”
RSFA	“I do not see how I can apply what I've discovered”
SIDIHub	“Very interesting and inspiring as it was a new topic for me.”
Trustless Democracy	“I believe my high level of engagement positively contributed to my understanding and appreciation of the topic.”
VeriRecruit	“The Inspiration talk was nice but I didn't feel that was linked with the project, maybe was better to have it later on in the project when would be more profitable.”
GUARDIAN	“The presentation was highly informative and covered significant legislative efforts within the EU, which are crucial for understanding the regulatory landscape affecting large corporations and market compliance.”

TABLE 14. SOME COMMENTS ON THE INSPIRATIONAL TALK SESSIONS FROM THE 2ND COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Flipped Classroom Session

The evaluation of the Flipped Classroom Sessions conducted during the first stage of the OnCampus Programme was reported by participating teams through feedback forms on the Sploro platform.

The table that follows presents the scores for the Flipped Classroom sessions, as evaluated by the participating teams of the first cohort, with scores ranging from 0 to 10.

Team	Flipped Classroom Score
D3ICA	7
EBSI-CAN	10
INTEROP4DID	1
SBAS	7
EvORAN	8
DDIP	8

SNDS	8
APSIDE	9
Average Score	7.25

TABLE 15. SCORES OF THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM SESSION FROM THE 1ST COHORT.

Similarly, Table 16 presents the scores, ranging from 0 to 10, for the second cohort's Flipped Classroom sessions, as assessed by the participating teams.

Team	Flipped Classroom Score
DES	8
DDP-CRC	9
HPQCSI	10
Melisseus	10
RSFA	0
SIDIHub	8
Trustless Democracy	8
VeriRecruit	8
GUARDIAN	9
Average Score	7.78

TABLE 16. SCORES OF THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM SESSION FROM THE 2ND COHORT.

The average score of the flipped classroom sessions, as evaluated by every team of the first cohort, is 7.25 out of 10. In a similar evaluation, the teams of the second cohort rated the flipped classroom sessions even higher, with an average score of 7.78 out of 10. These ratings underscore the effectiveness and positive impact of the flipped classroom approach, reflecting its success in engaging participants across both cohorts.

The following tables provide comments about the Flipped Classroom sessions from the teams of the first and second cohort experiments.

Team	Comment
D3ICA	“...quite dynamic and good intro to BMC. However, it would have been more efficient to get the info in advance in order to have a longer working sessions during the classroom.”
EBSI-CAN	“The insights from the team were used for the first draft of the canvas, followed by a team meeting to verify the inputs and suggestions.”
INTEROP4DID	“We already did similar excercises in the past.”
EvORAN	“As I am from the academic world, the Canvas model and other business models are quite new for me... This is the reason why I took a lot of things from the flipped classroom... I learnt that it is possible to do open research but also to create products oriented to business. Also, the way that Canvas can be done is an important starting point for this business-oriented vision.”
DDIP	“The workshop prompted contemplation regarding the strategic positioning of our solution.”
SNDS	“...during the Flipped Classroom we made many changes to our original plan, based on the talk and the discussion of other canvasses.”
APSIDE	“The flipped classroom was very interesting and enabled us to acquire new knowledge from practical activities.”

TABLE 17. SOME COMMENTS ON THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM SESSION FROM THE 1ST COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Team	Comment
DES	“...I believe my participation has been strong and has contributed to my learning experience.”
DDP-CRC	“...this was very helpful to create the Business Model Canvas and we had the opportunity to present our canvas and received immediate feedback.”
HPQCSI	“It was an enjoyable experience to discuss and work on the development of a startup. It was interesting to consider the idea of developing a startup from an open source project.”

Melisseus	“... The flipped classroom was helpful for us and help us understand much better where we are...”
RSFA	“... All this sounds pretty basic, academic and generic.”
SIDIHub	“It was extremely useful to be able to start brainstorming on the business model canvas and at the same time gain inspiration from what the other teams are thinking of.”
Trustless Democracy	“I have actively engaged with the course materials. During class discussions and activities, I have contributed to the learning process.”
VeriRecruit	“The Flipped Classroom was an important class since it is the basis for starting a business.”
GUARDIAN	“We ... participated in the proposed activity by providing the first version of the GUARDIAN BMC.”

TABLE 18. SOME COMMENTS ON THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM SESSION FROM THE 2ND COHORT EXPERIMENTS.

Video Lectures

Video lectures, as specified in the D4.1. Service Booklet deliverable, are online recorded sessions on the Sploro platform that explain the Lean LaunchPad theory by Steve Blank, providing teams with flexible access to 10 lectures on essential business development topics over the first six months of the programme.

The monitoring of video lecture views is conducted through the dashboards available on the Sploro platform. When performing the monitoring, the time spent watching each lecture is taken into account to mark it as viewed. By default, the platform marks a lecture as viewed once it has been opened, without considering the actual viewing time.

The table below presents the scores given by each team of the first cohort to the video lectures. These evaluations are based on a scale from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating "very relevant," 4 "relevant," 3 "neutral," 2 "somewhat relevant," and 1 "not relevant." These scores reflect the teams' assessments of the relevance and applicability of the video lecture content to their projects. The average score given to the video lectures by the teams of the first cohort is 3.50.

Team	Video Lectures Score
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D3ICA	4
EBSI-CAN	5
INTEROP4DID	3
SBAS	4
EvORAN	3
DDIP	1
SNDS	5
APSIDE	3
Average Score	3.50

TABLE 19. SCORES OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE VIDEO LECTURES FROM THE 1ST COHORT.

Similarly, the table below displays the ratings provided by each team of the second cohort for the video lectures. The average rating for the second cohort is 4.11, which is higher than the average rating given by the first cohort teams. This suggests that, on average, teams from the second cohort found the video lecture content to be more relevant and applicable to their projects compared to the first cohort.

Team	Video Lectures Score
DES	4
DDP-CRC	4
HPQCSI	3
Melisseus	5
RSFA	5
SIDIHub	3
Trustless Democracy	4
VeriRecruit	5
GUARDIAN	4
Average Score	4.11

TABLE 20. SCORES OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE VIDEO LECTURES FROM THE 2ND COHORT.

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Interviews With the Ecosystem

The table below illustrates the number of interviews conducted by each team of the first cohort with relevant industry agents, categorised by stage as of May 31, 2024. These interviews are integral to understanding the engagement and networking efforts of each team within the respective stages of their program participation.

The monitoring of the number of relevant interviews with the ecosystem conducted by each participating experiment is carried out by coaches during coaching sessions with every team. Teams must provide proof of the interviews, such as a screenshot of an online meeting or a photo from an offline meeting. Both coaches and teams report the number of conducted interviews through feedback forms on the Sploro platform, with coaches reporting monthly and teams reporting after every stage of the programme. The programme rules suggest a minimum of five interviews per month multiplied by the programme's duration in months. Teams have the flexibility to spread the interviews over time as suits them best. The total number of interviews conducted by each team is evaluated at the end of the OnCampus Programme's last stage, which determines the payment made to the team.

The final data on the number of interviews will be available in the Final Report, as a mandatory milestone.

The numbers below are tentative and based on the information shared by the beneficiaries with their coaches and the activity leader.

Team	Total as of May 2024
D3ICA	40
EBSI-CAN	37
INTEROP4DID	50
SBAS	45
EvORAN	35
DDIP	*1
SNDS	24
APSIDE	16

TABLE 21. NUMBER OF MONTHLY INTERVIEWS WITH INDUSTRY AGENTS CONDUCTED BY EACH TEAM OF THE 1ST COHORT.

¹ Total number of Interviews verified by the team coach will be available at the DDIP Final Report

Similarly, Table 22 shows the number of interviews conducted by each team of the second cohort with relevant industry agents during the first two stages of the OnCampus Programme.

Team	Total as of May 2024
DES	15
DDP-CRC	17
HPQCSI	10
Melisseus	34
RSFA	27
SIDIHub	15
Trustless Democracy	15
VeriRecruit	5
GUARDIAN	10

TABLE 22. NUMBER OF MONTHLY INTERVIEWS WITH INDUSTRY AGENTS CONDUCTED BY EACH TEAM OF THE 2ND COHORT.

Business Model Canvas

Each team is required to develop a "Business Model Canvas," a strategic management and entrepreneurial tool designed to help describe, design, challenge, invent, and pivot their business model. The Business Model Canvas enables teams to visualize and communicate a simple story of their existing business model, design new business models and manage a portfolio of business models. It facilitates the balance between exploring new opportunities and exploiting existing ones. Throughout the programme, teams conduct interviews with potential customers to validate and invalidate hypotheses expressed in their Business Model Canvas, using it as a standard graphical support tool to document their development and validated assumptions based on these external stakeholder interactions.

The Business Model Canvas, being a mandatory element of the OnCampus Programme, is evaluated by the coach of each participating team using a scale of 0 to 10. The coaches report the scores and provide a qualitative assessment of any

obstacles or challenges related to the Business Model Canvas components (Timeline, Key Partners, Value Proposition, Key Resources, Key Activities, Customer Segments, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Cost Structure, Channels) for each team through feedback forms on the Sploro platform at the end of the second stage of the OnCampus Programme.

Below is the table presenting the scores assigned by coaches to the business model Canvas designed by each team of the first cohort of the NGI Sargasso. Scores range from 0 to 10, with an average score of 9.38.

Team	Coach	Score
D3ICA	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	10
EBSI-CAN	Marc Sansó	10
INTEROP4DID	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
SBAS	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	10
EVORAN	Juan Juan	9
DDIP	Juan Juan	7
SNDS	Marc Sansó	10
APSIDE	Marc Sansó	10
Average		9.38

TABLE 23. EVALUATION OF THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS OF EACH TEAM OF THE 1ST COHORT BY THEIR COACH.

Similarly, the table below shows the scores assigned by coaches to the business model Canvas designed by each team of the second cohort of the NGI Sargasso, with an average score of 8.56.

Team	Coach	Score
DES	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
DDP-CRC	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
HPQCSI	Juan Juan	8
Melisseus	Juan Juan	9

RSFA	Juan Juan	7
SIDIHub	Juan Juan	8
Trustless Democracy	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
VeriRecruit	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
GUARDIAN	Jordi Bosch i Garcia	9
Average		8.56

TABLE 24. EVALUATION OF THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS OF EACH TEAM OF THE 2ND COHORT BY THEIR COACH.

Feedback Surveys

To assess each team's progress and satisfaction with the service provided, we implement feedback surveys tailored for both the teams and their coaches. The teams provide their feedback at the conclusion of every stage of the programme, ensuring timely and relevant insights into their experience with the NGI Sargasso. Concurrently, coaches are tasked with evaluating each team on a monthly basis. This dual approach facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the programme's impact from both participant and mentor perspectives, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation to meet the evolving needs of all involved parties.

Question ID	Question Type	Question Text	Options	Word Limits	Required
1	SINGLE CHOICE	How many coaching sessions did the team participate in this month? (Please select 0, 1, or 2)	3		Yes
2	LONG ANSWER	Please provide a brief comment on the team's performance, including team alignment, challenges, and motivation.		200	Yes
3	LONG ANSWER	How is the progress of the Business Model Canvas work? Are there any obstacles or challenges related to its components (Timeline, Key Partners, Value Proposition, Key Resources, Key Activities, Customer Segments, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Cost Structure, Channels)?		200 / 50	Yes
4	LONG ANSWER	How many relevant Interviews with Industry Agents did the team conduct this month, and with whom?		200	Yes
5	SINGLE CHOICE	Were the programme-related activities beneficial for the team's progress?	2		Yes
6	LONG ANSWER	Share your feedback about the team and any additional comments you'd like to provide.			Yes
1	LONG ANSWER	How many interviews have you had during the last 3 months? With whom? What did you learn from your ecosystem? Are you facing any challenges organizing interviews?			Yes
2	SINGLE CHOICE	How relevant were the activities performed during this stage?	5		Yes
3	SINGLE CHOICE	Share your feedback on the effectiveness of your coaching sessions. (Options: Very relevant, Relevant, Neutral, Somewhat relevant, Not relevant)	5		Yes
4	LONG ANSWER	Provide a brief justification for your rating.		200	Yes
5	LONG ANSWER	Please share an update on the achievement of KPIs by Stage 3 by KPI.			Yes
6	LONG ANSWER	How close are you to achieving your Individual KPIs by Stage 4? Are you facing any challenges? Please provide a brief update by KPI.			Yes

FIGURE 6. EXAMPLES OF THE FEEDBACK FORMS FOR COACHES AND TEAMS

Lessons learnt

WP4 : ONCAMPUS PROGRAMME

Lesson learned from First call OnCampus planning and consortium suggestions

Selection

- ✓ Request phone number and email of the legal representative.
- ✓ Request emails of team members to be invited to the different activities.
- ✓ Call for Experts/ Mentors at the website?

Onboarding

- ✓ Clearly define that Individual KPIs should differ from program KPIs.
- ✓ Invite coaches to the onboarding session.
- ✓ Provide clear information about the tools (platform facilities, feedback surveys, document drops, video lectures, webinar recordings).
- ✓ Enroll participants to the Acceleration App at the onboarding session to ensure platform access.
- ✓ Reminder at the end of Stage 3 about beneficiaries' duties.

FIGURE 7. LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE FIRST COHORT ON-CAMPUS PLANNING.

The consortium meets weekly, allowing brainstorming and rapid implementation of lessons learned or ideas of improvement, facilitating agile communication and decision-making.

The lessons implemented for the second cohort showed a more efficient development of the programme, teams and mentor relationships, achieving programme deadlines and a smother evolution of the programme.

Conclusions

The NGI Sargasso Programme has demonstrated significant success in fostering innovation within the Next Generation Internet ecosystem. Through support mechanisms, including coaching, mentoring, inspirational talks, and flipped classroom sessions, the programme has effectively guided participants towards achieving their business and innovation goals.

Key outcomes

- 1. High participant satisfaction: Feedback from participants indicates a high level of satisfaction with the support and resources provided. Coaching sessions received particularly high ratings, reflecting their critical role in participant progress.**
- 2. Positive feedback on mentoring and training: The mentoring sessions and inspirational talks have been well-received, contributing to the development of strategic thinking and creativity among participants.**
- 3. Business Model Canvas: The integration of the Business Model Canvas as a core component has been instrumental in helping teams structure their business models and validate their hypotheses through real-world feedback.**

Lessons learnt

- 1. Iterative improvement: The programme's iterative approach, incorporating regular feedback and retrospective workshops, has allowed for continuous improvement. Adjustments based on participant feedback, as well as internal consortium retrospectives have enhanced the overall effectiveness of the services provided.**
- 2. Engagement and participation: Maintaining high engagement levels among participants is crucial, addressing them individually in the online encounters of the trainings have been shown as key. Strategies to further increase participation and interaction during sessions will be implemented and explored, such as more meetings between cohorts at the beginning of the OnCampus programme, as well as more interactive exercises and debate classes combined with masterclasses.**
- 3. Customized support. Tailoring support to meet the specific needs of different teams has proven beneficial. Future iterations of the programme can build on this by offering more personalized coaching and mentoring experiences.**

Future Directions

1. Enhanced engagement strategies. **Developing new methods to boost participant engagement during sessions will be a priority. This may include more interactive and hands-on activities.**
2. Refined service offerings. **Based on feedback, the programme will continue to refine its service offerings, ensuring they remain relevant and impactful for participants.**

